

Development of a New Preventing Bedsores Mattress from the viewpoint of Kansei Ergonomics

Mitsuo Nagamachi*, Shigekazu Ishihara*, Masayuki Nakamura**, Kiyoshi Morishima***

**Hiroshima International University*

Higashi-Hiroshima, Japan, nagmit@za3.so-net.ne.jp

*** Panasonic Electric Works, Ltd,*

Osaka Japan, nakamura.masayuki@panasonic-denko.co.jp

****Toyobo, Ltd,*

Osaka, Japan, Kiyoshi_Morishima@toyobo.jp

Abstract: Kansei Engineering was applied to develop a new mattress preventing bedsores (pressure sore). A variety of low rebounding mattresses have been used for clients, because softness is thought as better to heavy body pressure. The risks of bedsores are Pressure, Friction happened between body and mattress surface. The main cause is the blood stop due to pressure. Ergonomics and kansei engineering were applied to find the best mattress made of polyester fiber with 3-dimensional spring structure (named as Breathair). We constructed a new mattress using this material very effective to prevent bedsores and Stage II and III of bedsores were recovered from bedsores in a few weeks or a few months.

Key words: *Kansei Engineering, Kansei Ergonomics, emotional design, pressure sore, mattress design*

1. Kansei Engineering

1.1 Meanings of Kansei and Kansei Engineering

Nagamachi founded Kansei Engineering in 1970's at Hiroshima University. The term *Kansei* means customer's psychological feeling and emotion on a coming product. A customer has a vague image and feeling in his/her mind before going shopping, which is called "Kansei" in Japanese. The Kansei has broad meanings such as wants, needs, expectations, motivation and these feelings and emotion motivate people to purchasing behavior. If the person finds a good product matched with one of these feeling, he/she will be delighted to buy that product.

Kansei Engineering is defined as "a translating technology of a customer's feeling into design domain using statistical and engineering means [1][2]. He has developed more than forty of the new *kansei* products so far and those are divided into three categories, Invention, Innovation and Improvement, based on its unique feature of used technology.

1.2 Methodology of Kansei Engineering

Kansei Engineering is an approach to customer-oriented product development, in which the customers' emotional feeling data are transferred to design domain. Methods of Kansei Engineering is as follows:

(1) Kansei Engineering Type I

We often utilize this method in which we start hearing a company's target and concept of a new product

and finally to reach the design specifications. The most popular method of Kansei Engineering is Kansei Engineering Type I, which is described as follows[4] [5] [6].

Step1: Decision of company strategy on a new product development

Step2: Survey of similar products in the market related to company's new product domain

Step3: Collections of samples and making the candidate products.

Step 4: Collection of kansei words for kansei evaluation

Step 5: Execution of kansei evaluation

Step 6: Ergonomic and statistical analysis

Step 7: Setting-up of new design specifications

Step 8: Designing a new product Step 9: Execution of verification

(2) Kansei Ergonomics

If the customer emotion is focused in Ergonomics application added to Kansei Engineering, we concentrate to apply Ergonomics to realize the easy in operation.

(3) Kansei Soft Computing

An Application of Intelligent Engineering enhances the effectiveness of kansei design level. We utilize knowledge engineering, neural network model, fuzzy logic, virtual reality technology and others.

1) Kansei Engineering System, 2) Hybrid Kansei Engineering System, 3) GA Kansei Engineering,

4) Multi-layer Neutral Network Model, 5) Virtual Kansei Engineering

(4) Kansei Rough Set Model

This domain means an application of Rough Set Model into Kansei Engineering, which Pawlack [3] founded in Poland which is feasible to find an inventive design derived from the vague and uncertain feeling.

2. Applications of Kansei Engineering

Because Kansei Engineering stands on the customer kansei orientation, all developed products have been fitted in the market. Kansei Engineering is applicable to any kinds of industries and it has been applied into Automotive, Construction Machine, Home Electric Appliance, Costume, Cosmetics, Food, Shoes, House industries and urban planning as well. Kansei Engineering is very powerful for developing the new product and also it is very productive in packaging designing as well [7] [8].

Nagamachi has developed more than forty *kansei* new products so far and those are divided into three categories, Invention, Innovation and Improvement, based on unique feature of used technology. The Liquid Crystal Viewcam made by Sharp is an example of invented kansei product. An R&D team of Video camera visited several homes and took pictures of farther taking attitude of their babies. The team found that they made bad postures for taking their babies. The team noticed that these postures needed high calories from the viewpoint of Ergonomics and Kansei Engineering. Accordingly the team created a new style of a video camera with rotating lens in 350 degree for keeping their good posture and a crystal surface behind to check easily taken picture. The liquid crystal viewcam was innovated to smaller and smaller in size, and a digital camera was emerged in the world based on the liquid crystal viewcam . Nowadays, 15 million digital cameras are produced in every year over the world. In this case, to keep better posture is an ergonomic need (namely, Kansei).

Figure 1. The invented process of a camcorder, Liquid Crystal Viewcam to a digital camera.

Another example is a new brassiere made by Wacoal, named *Good-Up Bra*. Wacoal asked Nagamachi to introduce Kansei Engineering to make a new product of brassiere. We conducted survey 2000 female monitors concerning their feeling when wearing any brassiere. About 80 % of subjects answered that they want to be “beautiful and graceful”. These kansei words were analyzed through Kansei Engineering techniques and we pulled out two principles: (1) Two breasts of emotional brassiere should be inside between two body sides, and (2) two breasts should be in parallel and towards a little upward. The new product, Good-Up Bra was exploded in the market and Wacoal has obtained a remarkable profit.

Figure 2. Ordinary brassiere (left) and new brassiere, Good-Up Bra(right). Kansei Engineering derived two principles in design,(1) two breasts should be inside both two body lines, and (2) two breasts should be in parallel and toward upward.

3. Pressure Sores

A development of a new kansei mattress for preventing pressure sores (bedsores or *decubitus ulcer*) is an innovative case of kansei product development and an application of Kansei Ergonomics. Any area of body with thin skin between skin surface and bone develops pressure sores, when this area of skin is squeezed to a mattress through bone and hard object like a body on the bed, chair and so on. In USA it is estimated that 1.3million to 3 million adults have a pressure sore. The unique portions developing pressure sores are sacrum,elbows, knees, ankles etc. The risks developing pressure sores are *Pressure*, *Friction* happened between body and bed (or chair), *Moisture*, *Bad nutrition* and so on. The most fundamental risk is inhibition of blood flow due to body pressure. The inhibited blood flow occurs when skin is rubbed against a bed, chair or other hard object. If skin condition is very bad surrounded with wet and unhealthy clothes by incontinence and of malfunction in nutrition, the area of the skin is easily broken.

Pressure sores are categorized by stages from the viewpoint of medicine.;

- (1) Stage I: The skin reddens, but it remains unbroken.
- (2) Stage II: Redness, swelling, and blisters develop.
- (3) Stage III: A shallow open wound (called pocket) develops on the skin.
- (4) Stage IV: The sore deepens, spreading through layers of skin and fats down to muscle tissue.
- (5) Stage V: Muscle tissue is broken down.
- (6) Stage VI: The underlying bone is exposed.

As much as the number of stage becomes larger, the medical stage means in very severity..

Figure 3. An example of pressure sore (Stage III-IV).

4. Pressure Sore Research

4.1 The First Step Research

Breathair which has three-dimensional spring structure made of polyester is controllable to adjust the size (length, width and height), density and spring strength as well in manufacturing, and it has high rebounding function. First we selected 22 different single type of mattress with different height and density and made 51 different combination types. Toyobo, Ltd has the patent of the breathair and provided us these experimental samples on the first stage experiment. We conducted experiments on the kansei evaluation in Kansei Ergonomics laboratory of Hiroshima International University [9].

Figure 4. Breathair material (left) and a sample of mattress (right).

We measured body pressure for each type mattress using a sheet type FSA (Force Sensitive Applications) pressure measure. At the measurement, a subject records his/her own feeling on the 5-point kansei SD scaling. The questionnaire items of the kansei SD survey are as the followings:

- (1) Flat and soft feeling, (2) Body sinking feeling, (3) Capable to take a good sleeping, (4) Easily roll over on the

Figure 5. A scene of FSA measurement

mattress, (5) Comfortable, (6) Feel premium, (7) Feel elegance, (8) Feel high price.

All subjects lie down on each mattress and his/her body pressure was measured for 10 min. After FSA measurement, he/she was still on the bed with recording his/her kansei investigation. Five students and one old subject with weight from 40 to 108 kg were employed for the experiment.

After the experiment, we divided all mattresses into two categories, better and worse ones from the viewpoint of FSA and kansei survey results. We found 7 were better ones among 22 single mattresses and 21 better ones among 51 double layers. The better mattress implies that it scored 5-point in the kansei record and with very light body pressure. On the other hand, the worse mattress means less than 3-point in the kansei record with very heavy **pressure**. Figure 6 illustrates the worse (left) and better mattress on FSA measurement.

Figure 6. Examples of the worse (left) and better mattress (right).
The figures implies FSA pressure measurement results., which Pixie sign shows the strength of pressure.

As a result of the preliminary survey, the lower rebounding mattress resulted in sinking very heavy into bed and in hard body rolling. On the other hand, the high rebounding mattress was able to support a body and easy to roll over on the bed. The latter is more comfortable staying on the bed. Concerning pressure sore, self-movement on the mattress several times for an hour is inevitable for preventing pressure sore. However, the soft mattress is very hard to roll over and it develops pressure sore on the body very easily.

4.2 The Second Step Research

The objective of the second step research is to find good combinations for light weight people and for heavy weight people. Concerning kansei research on “Comfortable”, the 7 better single mattresses had the meaningful difference with $p < 0.00002$ compared with other worse mattresses. Mattress A 4555 was the best one as a single mattress and very suitable for a heavy person among single mattresses.

We compared 7 single mattresses for light vs. heavy subjects and 5 selected combination of double mattresses for light vs. heavy subjects. The subjects were divided into two groups, a group heavier than 60kg and the other less than 60kg. In addition to this, we compared those mattresses with different cover clothes. As a result of the research, A6030 was the best for light group and A4555 the best for heavy group with statistically meaningful difference. The combination of A6030+A4555 was also the best combination for both group, especially A6030/A4555 (A6030 upper and A4555 bottom) was appropriate to the light group, and vice versa to the heavy group. Accordingly as a consequence, a combination A6030/A4555 is able to use as “a reversible mattress” for the body weight, A6030/A4555 is suitable for the lighter group and A4555/A6030 suitable for the heavier group.

4.3 The Third Step Research

The objective in this step is a comparison of kansei candidate mattress with other mattresses, which are very familiar in the market. Namely we aim to compare our kansei products with competitors. There are a lot of competitor mattresses, but we decided to select the most well known ten mattresses from the market. We conducted the kansei evaluation experiment again for ten competitors and our two reversible mattresses, and we have surveyed the kansei evaluation and have measured the body pressure using FSA measurement. We employed the same five students and on old subject and used the same kansei evaluation sheet.

Figure 7. PCA chart for Vector 1-2

After getting data of the kansei scores and FSA data, those data were analyzed using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Figure 7 shows distribution of kansei words and sample scattering. The arrows show the directions of kansei words. The horizontal line means Principal Component 1 and the vertical one Principal Component 2. Two Principal Components become totally 82% in contribution. Then two components are enough to explain the data. There are many kansei words related to “premium””high-grade” etc around the Principal Component 1 and other kansei of “without pressure” ”don’t sink” ”roll over” around the Principal Component 2.

The Principal Component as the main factor has all kansei evaluated data of comfortable, Good sleeping, High-grade and Premium, which we can say this axis is the kansei component. On the other hand, The Principal Component 2 as the second factor means a continuity of Don't sink and Low pressure –Sink and High Pressure factor. This is also concerned with the kansei of Easy-in-rolling.

The X11 and X 12 are the real products sold in the market and these have the function of lower pressure even though these are lower rebounding mattress. The X1, 3, 7, 8, 9 made of polyurethane are located on the other side of the Principal Component 2, which mean heavy body pressure. Those are not suitable to care for pressure sore. The new mattresses developed by Kansei Engineering are located at just middle area of the Principal Component 2 concerning body pressure. These mattresses had around 25mmHg/cm in body pressure.

General speaking, the body pressure is said as good one, if the body pressure of it is lower than 33 mmHg/cm. Therefore, our new mattresses are very suitable for caring pressure sore. In Figure 7, there are very low body pressure mattresses like X1,X2 and X10. If a client lies down on one of these mattress, he/she feels that the body sinks down and he/she feels as if the mattress tucks up a body owing to the softness and to low rebounding function, though it has the function of low body pressure. In Figure 7, we can see the mattresses are scattered from lower to heavy body pressure alongside the Principal Component 2, From the viewpoint of kansei evaluation related to “Comfortable” and “Easy-in-Rolling, the mattress suitable for caring pressure sore would be not lower nor heavy body pressure, middle position between both sides.

5. Blood Flow Testing

5.1 Blood Flow

The most risky cause for developing pressure sore is blood stoppage owing to body pressure. The blood pipe within bone and skin is crushed owing to body pressure and then the delivery of nutrition and oxygen to body become very hard, sometime it will stop. Then skin *necrosis* develops. In the case of human without movement ability emerging pressure sore will be enough at least in two hours owing to this mechanism. After a long surgical operation, for instance for 8 hours or more, the client will have big pressure sore owing to the same reason [9].

We measured blood flow using the blood measurement for the new mattress and the most famous commercial mattress as well. A small and flat sensor was inserted just under sacrum of an old male subject . Figure 8 shows an example of 83 years old person's result..We obtained the following blood flow charts, upper in Figure 8 for a commercial mattress and the lower for the new product A6030N/A4555. The commercial mattress is a good one related to very light body pressure, but because it is made of a rubber material it surrounds a whole body softly and the client is very hard to move on the mattress. The blood flow chart upper in Figure 8 illustrates the survey result, a comparison of the most wellkown mattress, Alpha Pra, made of polyurethane and our new product, A6030N/A4555. During 30min. testing, there happened very small blood flow on Alpha Pra. However, we can see the big blood flow symptoms for 30min. three times occurred by his own movement on the new mattress. Though the soft mattress shows the lower body pressure, but the softness function prevents a client's body movement owing its tucking mechanism.. On the other hand, the higher rebounding mattress like the new product has medium volume of body pressure and it surely keeps a smooth body movement on the mattress,

Blood flow chart of Alpha-Pra(30min.) Blood flow on the new mattress, A6030N/A4555(30m)
 Figure 8 Comparison of blood flow on Alpha Pra and of the new mattress, A6030N/A4555d (for
 30min.)

which is able to secure delivery of blood flow.

6. Verification of the New Mattress

6.1 Verification

We conducted a verification research on the effectiveness about whether the new mattress has effectiveness for preventing pressure sore. In Japan there is Japan Pressure Sore Society and all members believe that the soft mattress with lower body pressure made of polyurethane would be the best one. The society has very strong power and it is very hard to persuade members of it that a higher rebounding mattress will be very useful for preventing pressure sore. We denoted 50 new mattresses to total five organizations, four national hospitals and a welfare facility. Those institutions have totally about 1000 beds and about 30% clients are over 60 years old. Japanese hospital system is like to transfer the clients to other smaller institutions after two or three weeks care and then it is not easy to do survey the pressure sore recovery for long time. We could collect about 40 pressure sore client examples and half clients died or were transferred to other smaller institutions during verification research. We are very happy to describe a story of a hospital which provided us all clients' data that used the new mattress (*Rakumat-air DX*). We should keep Japanese Act for keeping an individual information. But we obtained the clients permission from only this hospital. We obtained permissions from all clients and addition to this, they were cared in the same medical system in the hospital, we could compare these members recovery verification from pressure sore.

Our research started at the end of August, 2008 and was continued to the end of March, 2009, for 8 months. This hospital named "Akita Accident Care Hospital" has 250 beds. This hospital had 12 pressure sore clients at the beginning of the research and among them three clients died by its own illness. Two clients were transferred to other small hospitals. A client developed bedsore very severely, since then, which was in stage VI and she used to use an air-mattress. If her pressure sore becomes smaller and smaller, it was planned that she will use the new mattress.

Seven clients have recovered from pressure sore completely due to utilizing the new mattress. They are divided into two groups as a result according to the length of duration until complete recovery, short and long period groups. The short period group consists of 5 clients and the long period group consists of two clients. The short

group took 18-50 days (average 26.6 days) and the long group took 123 -158 days (average 140.5 days, 4.6 months). There is the statistical meaningful difference on the level of $p<0.01$ and the latter group took longer days five times as much as the former group did.

The short period group consisted of the clients who had Stage II-III bedsore, but the long period group of the clients had Stage III-VI. We can say that the difference in bedsore between Stage II and VI means difference in severity and important medical implications. A client of the longer group was recovered once from pressure sore, but owing to the bad treatment by the hospital the pressure sore became again very bad condition. This reason became a factor to be a longer period to recover completely

Figure 8 The short period group(left) and the longer period group (right) from complete recovery.

6. Remarks

The concern of the present paper is to show the implication of Kansei Engineering and an application of it to develop a new mattress for preventing pressure sore. Kansei Engineering is client-oriented technology for a new product. The kansei implies human want, need, expectation, feeling and emotion which are concealed in human mind. If we are able to grasp human feeling and emotion and implement them in a new design of a product, the customers are willingly to purchase it, because the new product will match with their feeling, emotion and expectation. We have developed more than forty new products through Kansei Engineering and all kansei products developed until today were successful in good selling in the market.

We have developed a variety of methodology for applying them to different design areas and in the present paper, we are concerned with Kansei Ergonomics, which is related to ergonomic approach in order to develop a product. In general, Ergonomics is inevitable to build up any kind of product from the point of view of easy operation. However, when a new product development strongly needs the ergonomic aspect, the method is named as *Kansei Ergonomics*. The new mattress preventing pressure sore is a typical case of this.

There is a lot of commercial mattress for pressure sore, but the manufacturers imagine that a soft and low rebounding mattress is better for these clients, because the low rebounding mattress is imagined that it is able to realize the low body pressure. This thinking way is misunderstanding. The pressure sore is developed by many reasons such as body pressure, friction, moisture, bad nutrition and so on, and the direct risk is stoppage of blood flow under the skin. Most of manufacturers think that a low rebounding mattress will pull down the body pressure as well. This is wrong. It is sure from Figure 7 that the low rebounding mattress is not always pull down the strength of body pressure. The level of body pressure is enough if it is not so high. The most important

solution of pressure sore is to keep blood flow. For this condition, the client should be permitted to rollover on the mattress.

We have important principles to develop a good kansei product for preventing pressure sore;

- (1) The product can keep body pressure distribution, which means it supports the body weight with the broader area of mattress surface, not with directly body-touched area.
- (2) It assists body movement on the mattress very easily and softly, because easy body movement on the mattress triggers the smooth blood flow.
- (3) A wet mattress influences severity of pressure sore. Then we developed a porous mattress for keeping air ventilation.
- (4) An insanitary mattress spoils the skin and develops the skin infection. It is very important that a mattress should be kept in good sanitary condition. The new mattress is very easy to wash by shower and easy to make dry.

In order to satisfy with these principles, we have developed a polyester fiber 3-dimensional spring mattress. This mattress has the higher rebounding function appropriate to keep body pressure distribution, which assists the smooth blood flow. This has a porous structure to facilitate air ventilation inside a mattress. Accordingly it is very easily to clean out and to dry. It is treated antibacterial and the very sanitary. Since the weight is very light, a nurse easily manages and operates it.

We followed a few steps to reach the final result. We thought the new mattress should be higher rebounding material and decided to utilize polyester fiber named “*Breathair*”, which is controllable to produce any type of 3-dimensional functions. As the ergonomic methods, we decided to measure body pressure using FSA measurement, which is a flat pressure measurement sensor with a computer, and to use Omron Healthcare HBF-362 for the measurement of blood flow [2](Buckle & Fernandes, 1998). At the first stage, we attempted to find the polyester materials to keep the lowest body pressure. After then, we applied Kansei Engineering to select very comfortable, good sleeping and easy rolling over on the material. As a conclusion, we find the best combination of A6030N/A4555N, upper one being soft and the lower one hard.

As the verification on the effectiveness of the new mattress related to prevention of pressure sore, we denoted 10 new mattresses to each five national facilities and have surveyed the process of recovery from pressure sore. From the beginning of this research, we desired to combine all of data with five organizations. Owing to Japanese law of keeping individual information and the different treatment of medical environment, we decided to treat only one hospital which had the highest number of bedsore clients.. All seven clients have recovered completely from pressure sore, though the duration of recovery was different from each other. It is sure that the recovery duration depended on the beginning level of bedsore severity. All five hospitals have informed that they have no bedsore clients at present, because all clients completely recovered from pressure sore. Medical doctors, nurses and others have had misunderstandings In addition to this they were so conservative in keeping their thinking way, which has hindered an innovative change for the ergonomic treatment of care of clients for a long time.

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